

Implementation of Twin Wire-Arc Spray as a Promising method for production of 316 SS powders for Additive Manufacturing Applications

N. Talebi¹, M. A. Kalateh¹, R. Soltani¹, F. Khodabakhshi¹, M. Nili Ahmadabadi^{1*}

¹ School of Metallurgy and Materials Engineering, College of Engineering, University of Tehran, Tehran, Iran

*(corresponding author email address: nili@ut.ac.ir)

Abstract- This study investigates the potential of Twin Wire-Arc Spray (TWAS) as a method for producing 316 stainless steel (SS) powders optimized for additive manufacturing (AM) applications. Particle size distribution (PSD) analysis confirmed a D50 of 57.55 μm , well within the range required for powder bed fusion AM. Over 95% of the powders exhibited high sphericity, as shown through scanning electron microscopy, enhancing their flowability—an essential trait for AM. Vickers hardness measurements revealed that the 316 SS powders produced by TWAS achieved a significantly higher hardness (384 HV) compared to conventional gas-atomized powders (273 HV), highlighting the high cooling rate of this process. Microstructural analysis of solidification behavior identified diverse structural formations, from dendritic to cellular to planar, corresponding to variations in cooling rates. Additionally, the presence of chromium in the powders contributed to a protective oxide layer, reducing porosity and enhancing corrosion resistance, both vital for AM applications. These findings underscore the suitability of TWAS for producing 316 SS powders with the structural and mechanical properties desired for powder bed fusion additive manufacturing.

Keywords – Powder production, Twin wire-arc spray, 316 stainless steel, Surface oxidation

I. INTRODUCTION

Thermal spraying refers to a group of material processing and coating techniques in which molten or semi-molten particles are projected at high speeds and temperatures onto a prepared substrate, where they deposit and form a coating layer. This layer is essentially an accumulation of particles that are sprayed and solidified on the surface [1]. Based on its microstructure, the coating can offer properties like electrical and thermal conductivity, resistance to high-temperature corrosion, and erosion resistance, making thermal spraying suitable for applications in electronics, aerospace, and automotive industries [2]. Thermal spraying methods include flame spraying, wire arc spraying, plasma spraying, and high-velocity oxy-fuel spraying (HVOF), each sharing three common steps: (1) Production of Molten Particles (Particles are melted in the gun) (2) Transfer of Molten Particles (Molten particles are propelled toward the target substrate) (3) Particle Deposition (The molten particles settle, splat, and form solid or porous regions that build up the coating

layer) [3]. These common features are the fundamental principles of thermal spraying processes. However, differences in the heat sources used in each method result in coatings with unique applications. Among these, wire arc spraying is one of the most cost-effective methods, which we will explain further. Wire arc spraying is a popular choice due to its high material and energy efficiency, low operating cost, and low equipment costs [4]. In this process, two conductive metal wires are continuously fed into the wire arc spray gun. The gun's geometry positions the wires close together—just tenths of a millimeter apart—so that when an electric current is applied, an arc forms at the wire tips. This arc heats the wires, melting part of the metal. The molten metal at the wire ends is then propelled out of the gun by a high-pressure gas stream, which also atomizes it into fine particles [2].

Most investigations into the wire-arc spraying process have focused on correlating process parameters with coating properties [5], while relatively few have explored the initial stages of melting, molten particle transfer, and particle formation [6]. Among these studies, most efforts have concentrated on understanding particle formation and modeling the process [7], with relatively few reports examining the microstructural and solidification characteristics of particles. Existing studies report asymmetric heating at the two electrodes, attributed to the arc attaching over a larger area on the anode, while heating remains more localized at the cathode spot; Therefore, the particles generated from the positive wire exhibit more spherical and uniform characteristics, while those from the negative wire tend to be more irregular and larger in size [8]. This heterogeneity in particle geometry results in varying in-flight droplet behavior. Specifically, larger particles possess greater inertia, which affects their velocity and heat transfer capabilities with the surrounding environment [9].

316SS is key in additive manufacturing thanks to its corrosion resistance and strength. While gas atomization is the main way to make 316SS powder, new production methods are being researched to improve powder quality and reduce costs. This research is important because powder characteristics directly affect the quality of 3D printed parts. Herein, in this work, Twin Wire-Arc Spraying (TWAS) was utilized for production of 316 SS powders. Micro- and Macrostructure of the powders were investigated. Also, particle size distribution of the powders and geometrical parameters such as circularity were measured and compared with other works.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Production of the 316 SS powders was performed, utilizing a SPARK 400 Twin Wire Arc Spray system. A commercial 316 wires with a diameter of 1.6 mm with the chemical composition presented in Table I was fed into the TWAS system, and then subjected to the arc ignition with the conditions are shown in Table II, to produce the powders. It is worth mentioning that the powders solidified by compressed air and there was a 3-meter vertical distance between the gun and the substrate in the chamber.

TABLE I: CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF THE 316 SS WIRE

Element	Cr	Ni	C	Mn	Mo	Si	S	P	N	Fe
wt. %	17.34	11.69	0.079	1.985	2.854	0.731	<0.001	<0.001	-	Balance

TABLE II: PROCESS PARAMETERS OF THE CONDUCTED TEST

Voltage	Current	Atomizing Gas	Atomizing Gas Pressure
27 V	150 A	Compressed Air	4 bar

Initial microstructure of powders was investigated through optical microscopy, utilizing Zeiss Axioskop 2. For this purpose, a randomly distributed sample of powders (without any intention in selection) was considered, and prepared for further polishing. The mirror-finished powders were etched, using Kalling's reagent for microstructural observations. More accurate investigations on the morphology of powders were performed through the Scanning Electron Microscopy device (Philips XL30S-FEG at 25kV), using a secondary electron detector.

Vickers microhardness measurements were performed at the center of the longitudinal section perpendicular to the deformation direction. To provide this, a load of 100 g was applied for a dwell time of 10s, and the mean microhardness values were obtained from the average of seven separate hardness measurements. It is worth mentioning that in order to avoid hardness trace overlapping, the 0.3 mm spatial interval between each measurement (on each particle) was noticed.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As shown in Fig. 1(a), the 316 SS wires are connected to a power source, entering the gun at a set distance and positioned at a 30-degree angle to each other to create an electric arc. Due to the higher current density (J) at the cathode surface, the arc attachment on the electrodes differs, resulting in one of the defining characteristics of TWAS – asymmetric melting of the wire tips. Specifically, the magnetic pinch force ($= J \times B$ which J and B present current density and magnetic force, respectively) increases with higher current density, leading to the formation of smaller particles from the anode.

In Fig. 1(b), the forces acting on the particles are illustrated: Force (1) represents gravitational force, directed downward due to the vertical positioning of the chamber. Force (2) is the drag force exerted by atomizing gas, known as aerodynamic drag. Force (3) is the electromagnetic pinch force, acting perpendicular to the current density and magnetic force generated by the arc. Lastly, Force (4) is the surface tension force [3]. The combined effect of these forces shapes the particles into droplets, which solidify into a spherical form as they travel through the chamber and are collected at the end.

Fig. 1: (a) Schematic of the gas atomization procedure in TWAS system, (b) detailed view of the arc, and the present forces applied to a droplet.

To examine the microstructure of the produced powder in greater detail, the solidification of particles will be discussed from a fluid dynamics perspective. The phenomenon of convective flow within a liquid droplet (depicted in Fig. 2), also known as the Hill spherical vortex, was first described over a century ago. The Hill vortex is defined as a fluid sphere with uniformly distributed rotational flow inside, characterized by spherical symmetry. This symmetry causes the flow to move uniformly along the central axis, with flow lines forming closed, concentric circles within the sphere [10].

In the Twin Wire Arc Spray process, the collision of molten droplets with the atomizing gas plays a crucial role in altering the structure and temperature distribution within the droplet. Due to the high velocity and significant density difference between the atomizing gas and the molten 316 SS droplet, this collision induces shear stress at the droplet's surface. This shear stress in the outer layers of the droplet creates swirling flows within it.

As the atomizing gas impacts the droplet, the velocity of the droplet's outer layers increases due to the applied shear force, while the inner layers, not directly exposed to the gas, move at a slower speed. This velocity differential across the droplet layers creates a shear gradient, ultimately resulting in swirling flows within the droplet.

These swirling flows transfer heat from the center of the droplet to its surface, enabling faster cooling of the outer layers. This increase in heat transfer rate can accelerate the solidification process. Any oxide formed on the droplet surface may enter the particle and mix with the molten 316SS through convection if unstable. The internal rotation of molten droplets in the TWAS process influences the oxide

content within the droplets and ultimately affects the composition of the final as-sprayed coating. Further investigation of the cooling rate and morphological characteristics of the resulting powders will be discussed in details.

Fig. 2: Schematic of the fluid dynamics and internal circulation around a fully molten floating droplet.

Fig. 3: (a) Particle size distribution of the synthesized sample. (b) Comparison between particle size distribution of the current work with different gas atomized 316 SS, performed by [11].

Fig. 3 (a) depicts the Particle Size Distribution (PSD) collected using the LPS diagram of synthesized powders, which informs us about particle size distribution. According to this diagram, it is clearly visible that the measured D_{50} of the synthesized powders is about 57.55 μm . This value of D_{50} , makes these

resulting powders a promising candidate for use in the powder-based Additive Manufacturing (AM) processes, according to the specified acceptable D50 window. Fig. 3 (b) shows the Particle Size Distribution (PSD) obtained from Laser Diffraction (LD) data for Gas-Atomized (G.A) 316 powder, produced for additive manufacturing applications [11]. Comparing the PSD diagram from the present study with that of gas-atomized powder indicates that the particle size distribution in the current work is well-aligned and meets desired standards.

It has been accepted that the powders for production of powders bed fusion applications must present a good flowability with particle interlocking, simultaneously. Herein, it has been proposed that narrow and wide PSD will result in insufficient packing density and reduced flowability, respectively. As shown in Fig. 3(b), present study exhibits an acceptable PSD rather than similar work [11], which confirms the preconditions for AM applications.

Moreover, Fig. 4, which presents the Vickers microhardness measurements of the current sample (384 HV) compared to previous work (273 HV) [11], indicates that the mechanical properties achieved here exceed those reported in previous studies. This hardness enhancement suggests the potential for improved part performance, making it promising for laser powder bed fusion (LPBF) applications. In addition, higher hardness of the powders would be as a result of high cooling rate of the process, which will be discussed in details [12].

Fig. 4: Vickers Microhardness of the synthesized powders, compared with GA 316 SS reported by Karmarkar et al. [11].

In addition to the “size precondition” for the nominated powders for use in AM, the powders must present a good flowability, meaning that the powder must have a smooth surface with a high sphericity to reduce the inter-particle friction and particle inter-locking. For this purpose, the circularity of the powders was calculated using ImageJ software (as shown in fig. 5 (a)), based on different SEM images of the powders. As can be seen, more than 95% of the resulting powders exhibit higher sphericity than the minimum required, which turns them into a suitable selection for AM. As shown, a significant portion of the powders fall within the acceptable range for use in LPBF [12]. Additionally, Fig. 5(b) compares the sphericity of powders produced in this study with that of gas-atomized powders. As it shows in the graph, the results demonstrate a promising outcome for usage in LPBF additive manufacturing. As depicted in Fig. 5(b), the present study introduces a more uniform geometric shape with a much lower sphericity parameter range, compared to previous study [11].

Fig. 5: (a) Circularity of 316 SS powders as a function of particle diameter. (b) Frequency distribution of powder sphericity in the present study compared to a previous study [11].

SEM images reveals that there are a few agglomerated satellites. Outer surface structure of the powders reveal complete structure, and the surface morphology presents a cellular-dendritic manner [11].

The surface morphology of powders (Fig. 6 (a)), consist of radial-like dendrites or parallel cellular structure [13]. Fig. 6 (b) shows that in some cases, the powder surface consists of polygon facets. This morphological variation can be attributed to differences in solidification rates, driven by particle size and instability induced by the atomizing gas. As particles move relative to the centerline of the wire-arc spray during atomization, they experience varying gas flow conditions, which lead to differences in cooling rates and thus, solidification modes [14].

In general, smaller particles, with their higher surface area-to-volume ratio, experience more rapid cooling. This accelerated cooling rate promotes an affinity for solidification due to increased heat extraction.

The solidification rate dictates the resulting morphology—whether cellular, dendritic, or planar. As cooling rates increase, the solidification structure progresses from dendritic to cellular and, under the highest rates, to planar. This trend illustrates how varying particle sizes and their individual solidification dynamics can lead to distinct microstructural characteristics, a critical factor in predicting material behavior in downstream applications [14].

To further investigate powder morphology, variations in secondary dendrite arm spacing (SDAS) were examined in detail. Flemings et al. [15] proposed a mathematical model to predict SDAS in stainless steels, which relates SDAS to the cooling rate as follows:

$$\lambda = m \times \dot{T}^{-n} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 6: SEM images of the resulting powders, with enlarged views of two different surface characteristics of synthesized powders.

Where (m) and (n) are material-specific constants, set to 65 and $\frac{1}{3}$, respectively, for stainless steels in this model [15]. Figure 7 (a) shows a semi-logarithmic plot based on this relationship. Additionally, SDAS was measured in relation to particle size using ImageJ software (Fig. 7 (b)), while the cooling rate of the powders was plotted against particle diameter using available data (Fig. 7 (c)). As shown in the figure, cooling rates increase as particle size decreases, which in turn affects the solidification mode. Specifically, as particle size reduces, the solidification mode transitions from dendritic to cellular, and eventually from cellular to planar. This finding is further validated by SEM images of the powders, which visually confirm the observed progression in solidification modes.

Another key factor in controlling powder quality for additive manufacturing applications is assessing porosity levels. In a study, Vaz et al. [3] investigated surface oxidation in four types of steel powders (70S-6,309L, 410NiMo and FeMnCrSiNi) produced by TWAS. They identified chromium content in the alloy's chemical composition as a significant factor influencing surface porosity and particle size.

Their analysis, supported by the Ellingham diagram and the prioritization of oxidation for alloying elements (Si, Mn, Cr, Fe, and Ni), alongside EDS observations, highlighted the effects of chromium on powder oxidation, explained as follows:

- Chromium in steel facilitates the formation of a thin, stable oxide layer, primarily composed of chromium oxide (Cr_2O_3), which acts as a passive film. This film functions as a protective barrier,

shielding the underlying metal from further oxidation and corrosion. By limiting the penetration of oxygen and moisture to the metal surface, this passive film effectively reduces oxidation rates.

- Chromium content also influences oxidation kinetics. Increased chromium concentrations stabilize the oxide layer, lowering oxidation rates by reducing oxygen diffusion to the substrate. Studies indicate that as chromium levels rise, oxidation susceptibility declines, enhancing the material's resistance and durability under corrosive conditions.

Fig. 7: (a) Measured SDAS versus calculated cooling rate, (b) Measured SDAS versus Particle Size, (c) Calculated cooling rate versus particle diameter.

In fact, 309L stainless steel (which has the closest similarity to 316 SS among the mentioned alloys) exhibits higher corrosion resistance compared to carbon steels, due to the formation of a protective chromium oxide layer.

It should also be noted that some chromium in 309L undergoes internal oxidation, a phenomenon absent in 70S-6 carbon steel and similarly observed in 316 SS. This internal oxidation of chromium

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contributes to variations in the oxide layer characteristics and impacts the overall corrosion resistance and durability of the material, distinguishing these stainless-steel alloys from carbon steel counterparts.

Fig. 8: Optical Micrographs of 316 SS Powder Showing Regions of Internal Oxidation.

Fig. 8 depicts the optical micrograph of the 316 SS. As mentioned repeatedly the microstructure consists of tiny dendrite and as aforementioned, presence of meso-pores would be evidence for partitioning of Chromium to the matrix-pore interface and formation of Chromium Oxide.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study successfully validates Twin Wire-Arc Spray (TWAS) as a promising method for producing 316 stainless steel powders that meet the rigorous requirements for additive manufacturing. The key findings and contributions of this work are summarized as follows:

1. The TWAS process yielded 316 SS powders with a controlled particle size distribution, centering at a D_{50} of $57.55 \mu\text{m}$. This distribution aligns well with the requirements for powder bed fusion, ensuring suitable powder flowability and packing density essential for additive manufacturing.
2. Over 95% of the powder particles demonstrated high sphericity and acceptable circularity, characteristics that are essential for efficient flow during the additive manufacturing process. This uniform spherical morphology enhances reliability in powder handling and deposition.
3. Analysis of powder microstructure indicated various solidification modes—from dendritic to cellular to planar—depending on the cooling rates experienced by different particle sizes. These microstructural variations can critically impact the mechanical and thermal properties of manufactured components.
4. The study underscored the role of chromium in creating a protective oxide layer that limits surface porosity and enhances corrosion resistance, factors that are critical for long-term performance in additive manufacturing applications.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. Pourmousa, J. Mostaghimi, A. Abedini, and S. Chandra, "Particle size distribution in a wire-arc spraying system," *Journal of thermal spray technology*, vol. 14, pp. 502-510, 2005.
- [2] A. P. Abkenar, *Wire-arc spraying system: Particle production, transport, and deposition*. University of Toronto Toronto, 2007.
- [3] R. F. Vaz, A. G. Pukasiewicz, H. D. Fals, L. A. Lourençato, and R. S. Paredes, "Study of particle properties of different steels sprayed by arc spray process," *Coatings*, vol. 10, no. 4, p. 417, 2020.
- [4] N. Hussary and J. Heberlein, "Atomization and particle-jet interactions in the wire-arc spraying process," *Journal of thermal spray technology*, vol. 10, pp. 604-610, 2001.
- [5] N. Hussary and J. Heberlein, "Effect of system parameters on metal breakup and particle formation in the wire arc spray process," *Journal of thermal spray technology*, vol. 16, pp. 140-152, 2007.
- [6] W. Tillmann, E. Vogli, and M. Abdulgader, "Influence of Atomization Gas on the Particle Formation During Arc Spraying with Cored Wires," *Thermal Spray 2007, Global Coating Solutions*, pp. 837-842, 2007.
- [7] M. Kelkar and J. Heberlein, "Wire-arc spray modeling," *Plasma chemistry and plasma processing*, vol. 22, pp. 1-25, 2002.
- [8] G. D. Lunn, M. Riley, and D. McCartney, "A study of wire breakup and in-flight particle behavior during wire flame spraying of aluminum," *Journal of Thermal Spray Technology*, vol. 26, pp. 1947-1958, 2017.
- [9] J. R. Davis, *Handbook of thermal spray technology*. ASM international, 2004.
- [10] D. P. Guillen, *Oxidation behavior of in-flight molten aluminum droplets in the twin-wire electric arc thermal spray process*. Idaho State University, 2005.
- [11] N. S. Karmarkar, V. V. Varadaraajan, P. S. Mohanty, and S. K. Nagendiran, "An Attempt to Understand Stainless 316 Powders for Cold-Spray Deposition," *Powders*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 151-168, 2023.
- [12] A. Leicht, *Aspects of building geometry and powder characteristics in powder bed fusion*. Chalmers Tekniska Hogskola (Sweden), 2018.
- [13] K. Wu *et al.*, "Solidification characterization of a new rapidly solidified Ni-Cr-Co based superalloy," *Materials characterization*, vol. 73, pp. 68-76, 2012.
- [14] N. Pryds and A. S. Pedersen, "Rapid solidification of martensitic stainless steel atomized droplets," *Metallurgical and Materials Transactions A*, vol. 33, pp. 3755-3761, 2002.
- [15] M. C. F. a. G. E. Nereo, "Macroseggregation: Part I," *Transactions of the Metallurgical Society of AIME*, vol. 239, pp. 1449-1461, 1967.